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Electrical Properties of Soil in Bohol: Basis for Automated Irrigation System

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Abstract

Irrigation is vital for Philippine agriculture, particularly in regions like Bohol, where water resources are under pressure due to competing demands and seasonal droughts. Despite introducing automated irrigation technologies designed to enhance efficiency, many areas still need to rely on updated manual methods, leading to water wastage and reduced productivity. This study explores the potential of automated irrigation systems to improve water use efficiency by evaluating soil's physical and electrical properties in Bohol's greenhouses. Specifically, it investigates soil texture, bulk density, pH, moisture content, and the performance of resistive and capacitive soil moisture sensors under varying conditions. Using a randomized complete block design, the research analyzed soil samples from greenhouses in six municipalities: Antequera, Bilar, Calape, Carmen, Jagna, and Loay. Laboratory experiments assessed soil properties, and a custom Arduino-based soil moisture meter was developed for sensor calibration. The study found significant variability in soil properties across locations, with sandy clay loam soils exhibiting the highest electrical resistivity and lower water retention than silty clay and clay soils. The findings highlight that soil pH varied from slightly basic to strongly acidic, and sensor voltage output inversely correlated with soil moisture content, reflecting changes in electrical conductivity. The results underscore the importance of selecting appropriate sensors and calibration methods for accurate soil moisture measurement. Recommendations include further testing for sensor variability, preference for capacitance over resistive sensors, and rigorous calibration procedures. Enhancing these practices will improve the effectiveness of automated irrigation systems and support sustainable agricultural development in Bohol.

Keywords: *automation, electrical properties, irrigation, moisture, sensors, and soil*

Introduction

Irrigation plays a crucial role in Philippine agriculture, ensuring the growth and productivity of crops in a country where water resources are increasingly strained. As the demand for water rises due to industrial, municipal, and environmental needs, less water remains available for agricultural purposes. This scarcity is exacerbated during periods of drought or emergency, making efficient water delivery, allocation, and application essential. Consequently, achieving efficiency in irrigation requires a systematic water management program (DOST-FNRI, 2016).

Currently, Philippine agriculture relies heavily on conventional irrigation systems, where farmers use manual techniques for crop production. These manual methods are time-consuming and often lead to water wastage. In contrast, recent advancements in irrigation, such as automated irrigation systems, have been introduced to enhance water usage efficiency by monitoring soil moisture levels to optimize agricultural crop irrigation (Lailhacar et al., 2005). Furthermore, the transition from manual to automated systems represents a significant improvement in water management practices.

In Bohol, approximately 13,000 hectares of high-value crops were planted in 2017 out of a total of 273,950 hectares of agricultural land. Despite this, the production volume of high-value crops decreased by 20%, from 103,500 metric tons in 2013 to 86,000 metric tons in 2017 (PSA, 2018). To address this decline, the Department of Agriculture (DA) has supported the development of high-value crops through the High-Value Crops Development Program. This program includes grants for greenhouse structures to qualified farmers' associations, cooperatives, and Local Government Units (LGUs) (Colina, 2016; Cruspero, 2019). Moreover, greenhouse technologies for high-value crop production offer an alternative method to complement the current industry and address challenges leading to reduced production areas (Shaw & Cantliffe, 2003).

The adoption of technology, including controlled irrigation systems, represents a key improvement over traditional methods in managing high-value crop production (Ntirenganya, 2017). However, the influence of soil properties on irrigation practices is significant yet often underestimated (Israelsen, 2010). Soil moisture is a critical characteristic for evaluating irrigation needs, run-off susceptibility, and plant-available water (Bosch, 2004). Advances in electronics and information technology in agriculture now allow for easy monitoring of soil-water conditions using sensors, thereby enhancing irrigation efficiency.

Sensors are the most important and basic component of an automated irrigation measurement system (Abraham et al., 2000). Various methods, including laboratory and field techniques as well as remote sensing, are available to measure soil moisture content. For rapid and accurate measurements, soil moisture sensors are recommended (Garg et al., 2016). Additionally, affordable electromagnetic, capacitive, and resistive sensors are available, though they require thorough calibration relative to soil types (Rende & Blage, 2002). Given the absence of data on the electrical characteristics of different soils in Bohol for automated irrigation purposes, this study was conducted using two types of sensors to fill this gap.

Moreover, the legal framework supporting irrigation and water management in the Philippines includes Republic Act No. 8435, known as the Agricultural and Fisheries Modernization Act (AFMA) of 1997, which prioritizes irrigation research and development. It emphasizes the development of effective, appropriate, and efficient irrigation and water management technologies. Additionally, Presidential Decree No. 1067, known as The Water Code of the Philippines, and Republic Act No. 8041, the National Water Crisis Act of 1995, underscore the critical role of water in national development and necessitate active government intervention to improve water resource management.

In light of the challenges and opportunities in irrigation management and the significant role of technological advancements, this study aims to explore the potential of automated irrigation systems in enhancing water use efficiency in Bohol's agricultural sector. By examining soil moisture levels and the performance of different soil moisture sensors, this research seeks to contribute to the sustainable and efficient use of water resources in agriculture, ultimately supporting the productivity and livelihood of farmers in the region.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the physical and electrical properties of soil in the greenhouses within the province of Bohol as a basis for Automated Irrigation System. Specifically, the study had sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the physical properties of soil in the greenhouses of Bohol in terms of texture, bulk density, soil pH and moisture content at field capacity and at wilting point?
2. What are the electrical properties of soil in the greenhouses of Bohol in terms of resistivity and voltage output at different moisture levels using resistive and capacitive-type sensors?
3. Are there significant differences in the physical properties of soil among greenhouse locations?
4. What are the electrical characteristics of the different soil types in Bohol at different moisture levels?

Methodology

Research Design

The determination of soil physical properties was conducted in the laboratory using established protocols and a single-factorial experiment in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The factor under investigation was the greenhouse location, categorized into six levels based on soil series. The experiment was replicated three times.

Laboratory procedures were adapted to measure the capacitance and resistivity of soils at various moisture levels using electronic devices. Through programming, an automated measuring device was developed utilizing an Arduino-based Capacitance and Resistance meter.

Arduino-based Soil Moisture Meter

The soil moisture meter was designed with a programmable microprocessor using the open-source Arduino platform. It comprises three main electronic components: the Arduino Uno microprocessor, a data logger, and sensors. The system operates on a 5V direct current (DC) power supply. An IT expert developed a custom computer program that was uploaded to the processor using Arduino version 1.8.1 software to ensure the hardware functioned as intended. The interfacing process followed the concept diagram presented below.

Figure 1. *The conceptual diagram of the interfacing*

Participants

There were 28 DA-distributed and DA-supported greenhouses in the province of Bohol (Cruspero, 2019). These were distributed to qualified institutions, organizations, farmers' associations, and cooperatives in the province's three (3) districts.

Source: Cruspero, 2018

Figure 2. Greenhouse locations in the province of Bohol

Since some of these locations had similar soil types, categorization was performed to reduce the number of study sites. The existing soil map of the province, based on soil series, was used for this categorization.

Source: Provincial Planning & Development Office

Figure 3. Soil map based on soil series existing in the province of Bohol

As shown in Figures 2 and 3, overlaying maps revealed six categories based on soil series across sixteen municipalities where greenhouses were located, as presented in Table 1. The information was tabulated by municipality and soil series to identify the sampling sites. Representative municipalities and greenhouse locations were selected based on accessibility (e.g., along or near primary roads). Based on route and location analysis, greenhouses in Antequera, Bilar, Calape, Carmen, Jagna, and Loay were chosen as the sampling and study sites.

Table 1
Identified Soil Series by Municipality/Greenhouse Locations

Municipality	Soil Series
Albur	Lugo Clay
Antequera	Bolinao Clay
Baclayon	Lugo Clay
Bilar	Batuan-Faraon Clay
Calape	Calape Clay
Carmen	Ubay Clay
Cortes	Bolinao Clay
Jagna	Annam Clay
Loay	Lugo Clay
San Miguel	Ubay Clay
Tagbilaran (Dao)	Faraon Clay
Tagbilaran (Tiptip)	Faraon Clay
Talibon	Ubay Clay
Trinidad	Ubay Clay
Tubigon	Calape Clay
Ubay	Ubay Clay
Ubay	Ubay Clay
Valencia	Calape Clay

Soil physical properties determination was performed at the Soil Laboratory of Bohol Island State University – Bilar Campus, considering the facilities required in the analysis.

Instrument

Soil characterization in the study area involved the use of various instruments, tools, and materials, including a spade or auger (screw, tube, or post-hole type), core sampler, sampling bags, plastic trays or buckets, balance, sampling cans or other containers (sufficient for three per horizon plus extras in case some cans bent), permanent markers, wood blocks, nails, pencils or pens, sealable plastic bags, jars, and other containers for storing samples and extra soil. Additional equipment included a drying oven, graduated cylinders, water (or possibly alcohol if soil samples contained twigs), a #10 sieve (2 mm mesh openings), latex gloves, paper for catching sieved soil, a rolling pin, hammer or other utensils for crushing peds and separating particles, trowels, shovels, or other digging devices, one copy of the bulk density data sheet per horizon, paper or cloth wipe towels, dry sieved soil, 2 liters of distilled water, three 250 mL beakers, one empty 2-liter plastic bottle, a hydrometer, thermometer, plastic wrap (or another cover for cylinders), a 100-mL graduated cylinder, soil dispersing agent, 500-mL clear cylinders, a squirt bottle for washing soil out of beakers, meter stick, and a digital weighing scale with an accuracy of 0.1 grams.

For the calibration of the soil moisture sensor, the materials used included a shovel and bulk soil container (one shovel and one container for each soil type) for field soil collection and air drying, a calibration container, the Arduino-based soil moisture meter and data logger, a volumetric soil sampler, soil drying containers (at least three replicates per soil type), a digital weighing scale or mass balance, and a laboratory oven.

Procedure

Considering that the recipients of the greenhouses distributed or granted by the Department of Agriculture (DA) were the study's key informants, a formal letter requesting permission to conduct soil sampling, site characterization, and validation was personally handed to the officer-in-charge of the concerned agency.

With approval from the Office of the Department of Agriculture, the Municipal Mayor signed a communication letter to the Municipal Agriculture Office (MAO) seeking permission to conduct the study according to the specified schedule at the barangay where the greenhouse was located. The approved communication letter was the legal document authorizing the soil sampling and systems field evaluation.

Data Analysis

The data on soil particle size distribution was processed to calculate the statistical average. The averages from the three measurements or replications of each particle were used to determine the texture using the soil triangle. The laboratory results on soil pH, bulk density, resistivity, and moisture content were processed and expressed as statistical averages. The data on voltage outputs from the two sensors were graphed against soil moisture content. This graph represents the sensors' characteristics at different moisture levels.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm happened to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data to identify the soil's physical and electrical properties in Bohol as the basis for automated irrigation systems. Properties used to describe the soil physically are soil texture, bulk density, and soil pH. For electrical properties, voltage outputs and resistivity were used. Sensor calibration results were also presented and discussed in this chapter.

Soil Texture

Based on the soil map of Bohol by soil series, all municipalities with greenhouses, as indicated in Table 3, have clayey soil. Laboratory textural analysis confirmed this classification.

Table 2 shows that the greenhouses in Bilar, Carmen, Calape, and Jagna have clay-textured soil characterized by a high percentage of fine particles. This soil type exhibits high water absorption and retention capacity (Rende & Biage, 2002). In these areas, soil clods swell rapidly upon water application, indicating significant water absorption and space-filling among particles. The soil becomes sticky when wet and forms hard clods when dry.

In contrast, the greenhouse in Antequera has sandy clay loam soil dominated by sand particles. Sampling at a depth of 10 cm revealed sandy soil textures, suggesting the presence of a possible bedrock below 30 cm. Weathering or subsurface water flow, possibly influenced by the nearby Mag-Aso Falls, may have contributed to the sand deposition in this area.

The analysis in Loay identified silty clay soil, indicating a dominance of silt particles with clay. Given the area's proximity to the sea and its elevation of approximately 35 meters above sea level, this soil type likely results from silt deposition during the rainy season or flood events (mapcoordinates.net).

Table 2. Soil Textures inside Greenhouses of the Identified Locations by Municipality

<i>Name of Site</i>	<i>Sand Percentage</i>	<i>Silt Percentage</i>	<i>Clay Percentage</i>	<i>Soil Texture</i>
Antequera	50.59	17.21	32.19	Sandy Clay Loam
Bilar	34.50	13.99	51.51	Clay
Calape	35.37	17.37	47.26	Clay
Carmen	23.58	27.41	49.02	Clay
Jagna	36.32	20.50	43.18	Clay
Loay	13.00	47.48	39.52	Silty Clay

These soil textures indicated variability in electrical properties, particularly resistivity, due to differences in water-holding capacity. The amount of moisture held by soil particles strongly influenced electrical resistivity. Soil particles with poor water-holding capacity, such as sandy soils, offered high resistivity. Consequently, clay-textured soil, as found in the greenhouses of Bilar, Carmen, Calape, and Jagna, exhibited low resistivity.

Soil Bulk Density

The ratio of the mass of dry soil particles to their volume indicates soil compactness, which influences water movement and retention. The ideal soil for agricultural production typically has a bulk density ranging from 1.1 to 1.7 grams per milliliter (Rogers et al., 2015). According to the bulk density results, the soils in the greenhouses of the studied locations fall within this ideal range for agricultural production. However, the soils in the greenhouses at Antequera, Loay, Jagna, and Calape were more compact than those at Carmen and Bilar, based on statistical comparisons using one-way analysis of variance at a 95% confidence level. The bulk density of soils inside the greenhouses at Carmen and Bilar did not differ significantly. These findings suggest significant water movement and retention capacity variability across different locations.

Table 3. Soil Bulk Density inside Greenhouses of Identified Locations by Municipality

<i>Site</i>	<i>Replications</i>			<i>Average</i>
	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	
Antequera	1.219	1.266	1.144	1.210
Bilar	1.161	1.101	1.132	1.131
Calape	1.206	1.294	1.206	1.235
Carmen	1.020	1.032	1.006	1.019
Jagna	1.264	1.184	1.431	1.293
Loay	1.300	1.263	1.174	1.246

Soil pH

Soil pH measures the hydrogen ion concentration in the soil, indicating its acidity or alkalinity. Soils with high alkalinity are often sodic and dispersive, leading to slow infiltration, low hydraulic conductivity, and poor water-holding capacity. In dry conditions, such soils quickly deplete available water and become hard and cloddy. Conversely, strongly acidic soils exhibit good aggregation, internal drainage, and water-holding capacity, which only makes them suitable for some crops. Regular monitoring of soil pH is essential to optimize crop productivity.

Table 4 presents the pH values and descriptions of soil from greenhouses at various locations. The soils in the municipalities of Bilar, Carmen, Jagna, and Calape have pH levels ranging from 4.2 to 6.75, classified as slightly to strongly acidic. These locations show potential for crops due to their good water-holding capacity. While optimal pH ranges for crops vary, soils with pH values between 6.0 and 7.0, or slightly acidic, are generally considered best for agricultural production (USDA, 2011).

Table 4. pH Level of the Soil inside the Greenhouses of the Identified Location and the Corresponding Description

<i>Name of Site</i>	<i>pH Value</i>	<i>pH Indicator</i>	<i>Temperature* (°C)</i>
Antequera	7.55	Slightly Basic	25.70
Bilar	4.78	Strongly Acidic	25.60
Calape	6.75	Slightly Acidic	26.40
Carmen	4.20	Strongly Acidic	25.90
Jagna	5.96	Moderately Acidic	25.60
Loay	7.16	Slightly Basic	26.10

*. Temperature of the solution during the measurements

Electrical conductivity is positively related to the concentration of hydrogen ions in the soil (Mohd, 2014). This means soils with low pH levels exhibit high electrical conductivity due to the higher amount of hydrogen ions. According to the table presented above, the soils in the greenhouses of Bilar, Calape, Carmen, and Jagna exhibit higher electrical conductivity (or lower resistivity) than those in

Loay and Antequera.

Characteristics of Resistive-Type Soil Moisture Sensor

The behavior of sensor measurements at various soil textures and moisture contents was assessed following the calibration process. This behavior is depicted in the characteristic curves of the resistive-type soil moisture sensor. Table 5 presents the calibration data for the resistive-type sensor. As expected, the sensor voltage output exhibits a negative relationship with soil moisture content, as shown in Figure 4. This indicates that higher soil moisture results in lower voltage output. The increased electrical conductivity associated with higher water content means the circuit requires less voltage to meet the current demand. Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between the sensor voltage output and soil moisture content for different soil textures.

Figure 4. Characteristic curves of the resistive-type sensors at different soil textures and moisture content

Table 5. Calibration Data of Resistive-Type Moisture Sensor at different Soil Texture

Soil Texture	Soil Condition	Moisture Content, Vol. basis (ml/ml)				Sensor Voltage Output (Volts)			
		1	2	3	Average	1	2	3	Average
Sandy Clay Loam	1	0.10	0.095	0.10	0.10	2.08	1.98	2.08	2.05
	2	0.155	0.155	0.155	0.16	1.87	1.87	1.87	1.87
	3	0.44	0.44	0.435	0.44	1.84	1.84	1.82	1.84
	4	0.53	0.525	0.525	0.53	1.07	1.06	1.06	1.06
	5	0.535	0.535	0.535	0.54	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67
	6	0.55	0.55	0.545	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55
Silty Clay	1	0.03	0.03	0.025	0.03	2.06	2.06	2.07	2.06
	2	0.18	0.18	0.180	0.18	1.41	1.40	1.40	1.40
	3	0.31	0.31	0.310	0.31	0.54	0.55	0.54	0.54
	4	0.40	0.40	0.395	0.40	0.35	0.36	0.35	0.35
	5	0.53	0.53	0.525	0.53	0.34	0.35	0.34	0.34
	6	0.58	0.58	0.580	0.58	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32
Clay	1	0.07	0.07	0.070	0.07	2.08	2.09	2.07	2.08
	2	0.38	0.38	0.375	0.38	2.07	2.05	2.05	2.06
	3	0.49	0.49	0.485	0.49	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.95
	4	0.58	0.58	0.575	0.58	0.77	0.76	0.78	0.77
	5	0.61	0.61	0.610	0.61	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74
	6	0.65	0.65	0.650	0.65	0.50	0.50	0.49	0.50

Table 6. Statistical analysis of Data for Resistive-type Soil Moisture Voltage Output

Mathematical Function	Soil Types	Coefficient of Determination, R2	Regression Equation
Exponential	Sandy Clay Loam	0.6344	$Y = 1.071E-0.897X$
	Silty Clay	0.9246	$Y = 0.825E-1.461X$
	Clay	0.6082	$Y = 1.1621E-0.946X$
Linear	Sandy Clay Loam	0.716	$Y = -0.2612X+0.7369$
	Silty Clay	0.8608	$Y = -0.2668X+0.5615$
	Clay	0.7918	$Y = 0.2736X+0.7868$
Logarithmic	Sandy Clay Loam	0.6443	$Y = -0.288\ln(X)+0.4357$
	Silty Clay	0.9103	$Y = -0.25\ln(X)+0.222$
	Clay	0.7775	$Y = -0.326\ln(X) + 0.4709$
Polynomial	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8162	$Y = -0.342X^2+0.63X+0.29$
	Silty Clay	0.8827	$Y = 0.117X^2-0.522X+0.65$
	Clay	0.7922	$Y = 0.24X^2-0.339X+ 0.82$
Power	Sandy Clay Loam	0.5598	$Y = 0.3801X-0.978$
	Silty Clay	0.8506	$Y = 0.1341X-1.268$
	Clay	0.5733	$Y = 0.3896X-1.104$

Table 6 presents the relationship of the data used for the trend regression analysis. According to the table, the relationship between the data collected from the sandy clay loam soil (resistive sensor voltage output and volumetric water content) is best represented by a polynomial function, as the coefficient of determination is closest to 1 compared to other mathematical functions. Additionally, data from silty clay is more accurately graphed using an exponential function, while clay soil data is best interpreted using a polynomial function.

Characteristics of Capacitive-Type Soil Moisture Sensor

The behavior of sensor measurements across different soil textures and moisture contents was assessed following the calibration process. This behavior is depicted through the characteristic curves of the capacitive-type soil moisture sensor. Table 7 presents the calibration data for this sensor. As anticipated, the sensor's voltage output exhibits a negative relationship with soil moisture content, as illustrated in Figure 5. This indicates that at higher soil moisture levels, the voltage output decreases. The increased electrical conductivity of the soil, associated with higher water content, necessitates a lower voltage to meet the current requirements.

Figure 5 further illustrates the relationship between the sensor's voltage output and soil moisture content for various soil textures.

Figure 5. Characteristic curves of the capacitive-type sensors at different soil textures and moisture contents

Table 7. Calibration Data of Capacitive-Type Moisture Sensor at different Soil Texture

Soil Texture	Soil Condition	Moisture Content, Vol. basis (ml/ml)				Sensor Voltage Output (Volts)			
		1	2	3	Average	1	2	3	Average
Sandy Clay Loam	1	0.10	0.095	0.10	0.10	2.26	2.25	2.26	2.26
	2	0.155	0.155	0.155	0.16	1.30	1.29	1.30	1.30
	3	0.44	0.44	0.435	0.44	0.83	0.83	0.81	0.82
	4	0.53	0.525	0.525	0.53	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.77
	5	0.535	0.535	0.535	0.54	0.48	0.47	0.48	0.48
	6	0.55	0.55	0.545	0.55	0.39	0.39	0.37	0.38
Silty Clay	1	0.03	0.03	0.025	0.03	2.02	2.25	2.26	2.18
	2	0.18	0.18	0.180	0.18	1.07	1.29	1.30	1.22
	3	0.31	0.31	0.310	0.31	0.52	0.83	0.81	0.72
	4	0.40	0.40	0.395	0.40	0.51	0.76	0.77	0.68
	5	0.53	0.53	0.525	0.53	0.39	0.47	0.48	0.45
	6	0.58	0.58	0.580	0.58	0.35	0.39	0.37	0.37
Clay	1	0.07	0.07	0.070	0.07	2.56	2.54	2.56	2.55
	2	0.38	0.38	0.375	0.38	2.19	2.17	2.18	2.18
	3	0.49	0.49	0.485	0.49	1.15	1.16	1.16	1.16
	4	0.58	0.58	0.575	0.58	0.75	0.73	0.75	0.75
	5	0.61	0.61	0.610	0.61	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46
	6	0.65	0.65	0.650	0.65	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30

Table 8 shows the relationship of the data used for the trend regression analysis. Based on the table below, the relationship between the data collected from the sandy clay loam soil (Capacitive Sensor Voltage Output and Volumetric Water Content) can be plotted on the graph using an Exponential Function since the coefficient of determination is closest to 1 rather than the other mathematical functions.

Moreover, data from silty clay data can preferably be graphed using an exponential function, and data from clay soil can be interpreted using a polynomial function.

Table 8. Statistical analysis of Data Capacitive-type Soil Moisture Voltage Output

Mathematical Function	Soil Types	Coefficient of Determination, R2	Regression Equation
Exponential	Sandy Clay Loam	0.9043	$Y = 0.8895e^{-1.015x}$
	Silty Clay	0.9915	$Y = 1.1163e^{-1.628x}$
	Clay	0.7013	$Y = 0.9752e^{-0.765x}$
Linear	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8509	$Y = -0.27x + 0.6571$
	Silty Clay	0.8839	$Y = -0.2909x + 0.6108$
	Clay	0.8819	$Y = -0.2173x + 0.7314$
Logarithmic	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8522	$Y = -0.289\ln(x) + 0.3346$
	Silty Clay	0.9814	$Y = -0.318\ln(x) + 0.2574$
	Clay	0.7649	$Y = -0.222\ln(x) + 0.4484$
Polynomial	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8929	$Y = 0.113x^2 - 0.57x + 0.8$
	Silty Clay	0.9817	$Y = 0.2x^2 - 0.806x + 0.842$
	Clay	0.9197	$Y = -0.09x^2 + 0.03x + 0.62$
Power	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8491	$Y = 0.2661x^{-1.051}$
	Silty Clay	0.9059	$Y = 0.1611x^{-1.1612}$
	Clay	0.5501	$Y = 0.3612x^{-0.742}$

Soil Resistivity at different Moisture Levels

Soil electrical resistivity measures the resistance of soil to the passage of electrical current and is a cost-effective method used in precision farming. Soil resistivity is influenced by soil texture, moisture content, and temperature.

Unlike direct methods of measuring soil moisture, soil resistivity does not measure moisture directly but is an indirect indicator. There is a negative relationship between soil resistivity and moisture content; as soil moisture increases, resistivity decreases.

Table 9. Soil Resistivity at different Soil Texture

Soil Texture	Soil Condition	Moisture Content, Vol. basis (ml/ml)				Soil Resistivity (kΩ-cm)			
		1	2	3	Average	1	2	3	Average
Sandy Clay Loam	1	0.10	0.095	0.10	0.10	4600	4370	4600	4600
	2	0.155	0.155	0.155	0.16	3910	3910	3910	3910
	3	0.44	0.44	0.435	0.44	3250	3250	3213	3250
	4	0.53	0.525	0.525	0.53	358	355	355	358
	5	0.535	0.535	0.535	0.54	304	304	304	304
	6	0.55	0.55	0.545	0.55	253	253	251	253
Silty Clay	1	0.03	0.03	0.025	0.03	3760	3760	3133	3551.0
	2	0.18	0.18	0.180	0.18	1700	1700	1749	1716.3
	3	0.31	0.31	0.310	0.31	1665	1665	1692	1674.0
	4	0.40	0.40	0.395	0.40	1506	1525	1506	1512.3
	5	0.53	0.53	0.525	0.53	45.5	46	45.5	45.7
	6	0.58	0.58	0.580	0.58	2.78	2.81	2.81	2.8
Clay	1	0.07	0.07	0.070	0.07	3364	3364	3365	3364.3
	2	0.38	0.38	0.375	0.38	1528	1527	1528	1527.7
	3	0.49	0.49	0.485	0.49	1437	1437	1422	1432.0
	4	0.58	0.58	0.575	0.58	1329	1341	1329	1333.0
	5	0.61	0.61	0.610	0.61	52.3	52.5	52.3	52.4
	6	0.65	0.65	0.650	0.65	2.71	2.71	2.73	2.7

Figure 6. Characteristic curves of the soil resistivity at different soil moisture content

Soil texture also affects resistivity. Although management practices cannot alter soil texture, it is important to understand its interaction with resistivity. Sand typically has high resistivity, silt has medium resistivity, and clay has low resistivity.

Observations indicate that as moisture content increases, electrical resistivity decreases. Sandy clay loam, for instance, exhibits the highest electrical resistivity, indicating that it retains less water compared to silty clay and clay soils. Silty clay, with the lowest electrical resistivity, holds the most water.

Table 10 shows the relationship of the data used for the trend regression analysis. Based on the table below, the relationship between the data collected from the sandy clay loam, silty clay, and clay soil (Soil Resistivity and Volumetric Water Content) can be plotted on the graph using a polynomial Function since the coefficient of determination is the closest to 1 rather than the other mathematical functions.

Table 10. Statistical analysis of Soil Resistivity

Mathematical Function	Soil Types	Coefficient of Determination, R ²	Regression Equation
Exponential	Sandy Clay Loam	0.7739	$Y = 0.635e^{-3E-04x}$
	Silty Clay	0.8615	$Y = 0.74e^{-8E-04x}$
	Clay	0.8176	$Y = 0.9752e^{-0.765x}$
Linear	Sandy Clay Loam	0.8425	$Y = -9E-05x + 0.58$
	Silty Clay	0.9095	$Y = -0.0002x + 0.5544$
	Clay	0.8866	$Y = -0.0002x + 0.68$
Logarithmic	Sandy Clay Loam	0.7473	$Y = -0.13\ln(x) + 1.2603$
	Silty Clay	0.6987	$Y = -0.052\ln(x) + 0.7675$
	Clay	0.4519	$Y = -0.222\ln(x) + 0.4484$
Polynomial	Sandy Clay Loam	0.9402	$Y = -4E-08x^2 + 1E-04x + 0.52$
	Silty Clay	0.9121	$Y = 6E-09x^2 - 0.0002x + 0.6$
	Clay	0.9342	$Y = -3E-08x^2 - 6E-05x$
Power	Sandy Clay Loam	0.6566	$Y = 6.3783x^{0.428}$
	Silty Clay	0.408	$Y = 1.0566x^{-0.25}$
	Clay	0.2968	$Y = 1.0044x^{-0.167}$

The study conducted in the province of Bohol assessed various soil properties within greenhouses to evaluate their suitability for agricultural production. The findings are summarized below:

Soil texture in various greenhouses across the region varied significantly. In Antequera, the soil was classified as Sandy Clay Loam, predominantly composed of sand particles. In contrast, Loay's greenhouse soil was identified as Silty Clay Loam, characterized by a dominance of silt particles mixed with clay. Meanwhile, soils from greenhouses in Carmen, Bilar, Jagna, and Calape were classified as Clay Soil, indicating a high percentage of fine particles.

Regarding bulk density, all greenhouse soils fell within the ideal range for agricultural production. Nonetheless, statistical analysis (one-way ANOVA at a 95% confidence level) revealed that soils in Antequera, Loay, Jagna, and Calape were more compact compared to those in Carmen and Bilar.

In terms of soil pH, the soils in the greenhouses of Bilar, Carmen, Jagna, and Calape exhibited pH levels ranging from 4.2 to 6.75, classifying them as slightly to strongly acidic, which is generally suitable for crop growth. Conversely, the soil in Antequera had a slightly basic pH.

The calibration of soil sensors highlighted some notable electrical properties. It was observed that the sensor voltage output had a negative relationship with soil moisture content; higher soil moisture levels resulted in lower voltage output. Additionally, the resistivity of the soil varied with texture: sand exhibited high resistivity, silt medium resistivity, and clay low resistivity. Specifically, Sandy Clay Loam soils recorded the highest electrical resistivity, indicating lower water retention, whereas Silty Clay soils had the lowest electrical resistivity, reflecting higher water retention.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concludes that:

Soil Variability. The soil in Bohol's greenhouses exhibits significant texture variability, ranging from sandy clay loam in Antequera to Silty Clay Loam in Loay and Clay Soil in Carmen, Bilar, Jagna, and Calape. This variability affects water retention and agricultural suitability.

Bulk Density and Compaction. All study sites meet agriculture's ideal bulk density range. However, Antequera, Loay, Jagna, and Calape soils are more compact than in Carmen and Bilar, which may influence water movement and root growth.

Soil pH. Most greenhouse soils have pH levels conducive to crop growth, with Bilar, Carmen, Jagna, and Calape having slightly to

strongly acidic soils and Antequera having slightly basic soil. This pH range supports diverse agricultural activities but requires monitoring for optimal crop performance.

Electrical Resistivity and Moisture. Electrical resistivity is inversely related to soil moisture content, with higher moisture leading to lower resistivity. Sandy Clay Loam soils showed the highest resistivity and lowest water retention, whereas Silty Clay soils exhibited the lowest and highest water-holding capacity.

In summary, understanding these soil characteristics is essential for optimizing greenhouse conditions and improving agricultural productivity in Bohol.

Based on the study's findings, the researcher recommends the following actions for future research and practical applications:

Sensor-to-Sensor Variability Test. Conduct a variability test for different sensors to assess and validate the reliability of sensor readings, as similar sensors can produce differing analog outputs.

Preference for Capacitance Sensors. Prefer the use of capacitance sensors over resistive sensors. Resistive sensors are prone to corrosion due to electrolysis between the sensor and water, which can affect their longevity and accuracy.

Use of Oscillators for Capacitance Measurement. Employ oscillators to monitor capacitance changes, providing more accurate measurements of soil capacitance at varying moisture levels.

Increased Replicates in Soil Textural Analysis. Increase the number of replicates in soil textural analysis to achieve more precise and reliable results.

Additional Replicates for Physical Properties. Incorporate three or more replicates when identifying soil physical properties to ensure consistent results and reduce variability.

Homogeneous Soil Preparation for Calibration. Thoroughly mix water into the soil to achieve a homogeneous mixture before inserting the sensor. Maintain the bulk density of the soil sample to match the site's conditions, minimizing calibration errors.

Multiple Calibration Procedures. Perform calibration procedures three to five times to derive a more consistent calibration function and improve accuracy.

Comparison of Sensor Versions: Use different versions of moisture sensors to compare and validate the calibration functions generated, enhancing the robustness of the calibration process.

Protection for Capacitive Sensors. Seal the exposed edges of the SEN 0193 Capacitive Soil Moisture Sensor v1.2 with epoxy or a protective adhesive to minimize corrosion, maximize sensor accuracy, and reduce instrument errors.

Sensor Coverage. Ensure that the exposed parts of the capacitive soil moisture sensor are covered with a sensor cover to protect against moisture and prevent measurement inaccuracies.

Implementing these recommendations will enhance the accuracy and reliability of soil moisture measurements and improve the overall quality of future research.

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